

The Use of Sunlight Therapy to Improve Depression for Patients in a Skilled Nursing Facility

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Background

- WHO identified major depressive disorder as the leading mental disability worldwide
- Within nursing homes, prevalence of depressive symptoms 35% to 48.7%.
- Nursing home residents are confined due to global physical decline and immobility
- Sunlight demonstrates a positive benefit in individuals experiencing depression from Seasonal Affective Disorder

Purpose

- Develop, implement, and evaluate a sunlight intervention for older adults (OAs) suffering from depression, who reside in a nursing facility

Pathophysiology

- Depression is a disease that is linked to abnormalities in the function of the subcortical limbic system
- Hypothesized to have monoamine neurotransmitters deficiency
- The monoamines are dopamine, norepinephrine (NE) and serotonin (5HT)

Seasonal Affective Disorder

- Lack of sunlight causing increase melatonin, this impairs the hypothalamic suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCN)
- This dysregulation disrupts circadian rhythm and communication system
- Sunlight influences SCN regulates depression associated neurotransmitters, which supports circadian pacemaker in the brain

Sunlight and Light Therapy

- Sunlight therapy is an effective treatment for depression in OAs residing in nursing homes.
- There are no evidence-based guidelines on using sunlight for treating symptoms of depression among OAs within nursing facilities
- Adoption of guidelines for the use of sunlight in OAs could have a profound impact on depressive symptoms, as well as other comorbidities
- Several studies have reported an overall benefit of light therapy for individuals of all ages with non-seasonal depression

IOWA Model

Methods

- Pre and Post Design
- The project will seek to determine whether levels of depression among OAs decreases by using sunlight therapy provided five days per week for a duration of five weeks
- Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS): Short Form
- Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9)

Results

- Due to the COVID-19 pandemic and facility support, the project had to be placed on hold
- The risk of conducting the project was due to the high risk for significant adverse outcomes and mortality
- Reducing symptoms of depression in this vulnerable population through an evidence-based practice approach represents a significant opportunity to improve the quality of life for OAs

Evaluation

- In this pilot project, the difference in scores on the GDS and PHQ9 will be calculated to show the pre- and post-test comparison scores.
- A change between the pre- and post-test scores will be calculated

Discussion

- The project facility had many devastating losses due to the pandemic and was no longer able to accommodate the project
- The project will be completed as conditions improve and the restrictions on outside providers are lifted